

1 **Study of silica-structured materials as sorbents for organophosphorus**
2 **pesticides determination in environmental water samples**
3

4
5
6 Enric Pellicer-Castell¹, Carolina Belenguer-Sapiña¹, Pedro Amorós², Jamal El
7 Haskouri², José M. Herrero-Martínez¹, Adela Mauri-Aucejo^{1*}
8
9

10
11
12 ¹ Department of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, University of Valencia, Dr
13 Moliner 50, 46100, Burjassot, Valencia, Spain.
14
15

16 ² Institut of Material Science (ICMUV), University of Valencia, Catedrático José Beltrán
17 2, 46980 Paterna, Valencia, Spain
18
19

20
21
22 *Corresponding author: Dra. Adela Mauri-Aucejo
23

24 Tel.: +34963544016

25 e-mail: adela.mauri@uv.es
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48

49 **Declaration of interests:** none
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Abstract

A novel sorbent based on a UVM-7 mesoporous silica doped with Ti has been synthesized and used for solid-phase extraction of several organophosphorus pesticides in environmental water samples followed by gas chromatography coupled to a nitrogen-phosphorus selective detector. Thus, mesoporous silica materials doped with Ti and Fe as well as immobilized cyclodextrin silica-based supports were prepared and morphologically characterized by several techniques such as transmission electronic microscopy, nitrogen adsorption-desorption and X-ray diffraction. These sorbents were comparatively evaluated, and Ti25-UVM-7 material was selected as the best solid phase. After optimization of extraction parameters such as amount of solid-phase, type and volume of eluent, pH and ionic strength and breakthrough volume, recoveries between 81 % and 104.5 % were achieved, with RSD values below 7.8 % and 12 % for intra-day and inter-day repeatability respectively. Moreover, limits of quantification in the range 0.5-4.4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ were achieved for all target compounds using mass spectrometry detector. In addition, the developed method was applied for analysis of real water samples and it was validated with commercial C18 cartridges. Matrix effect was demonstrated in complex environmental matrices and the good reusability of synthesized material was also proved.

Keywords

Organophosphorus pesticides; Mesoporous silica; Solid-phase extraction; Gas chromatography; Water samples; Preconcentration

Abbreviations

OPP: Organophosphorus pesticides
GC: Gas chromatography
LC: Liquid chromatography
NPD: Nitrogen-phosphorus detector
MS: Mass spectrometry
LLE: Liquid-liquid extraction
DLLME: Dispersive liquid-liquid extraction
SBSE: Stir bar sorptive extraction
SPE: Solid phase extraction
SPME: Solid phase microextraction

1 TEOS: Tetraethyl orthosilicate
2 CTAB: Cetyl trimethylammonium
3 CD: Cyclodextrin
4 MeOH: Methanol
5 ACN: Acetonitrile
6 TEA: Triethanolamine
7 TBOT: Tetrabutyl orthotitanate
8 HRTEM: High-resolution transmission electron microscopy
9 EDX: Energy-dispersive X-ray
10 WWTP: Wastewater treatment plant
11 LOD: Limit of detection
12 LOQ: Limit of quantification
13 EF: Enrichment Factor
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Introduction

Organophosphorus pesticides have been widely used in agriculture to protect crops and plantations due to their insecticidal properties. However, after their use the remains of these pesticides can reach drinking or superficial waters affecting the human health as they show carcinogenic and mutagenic effects. Thus, the presence of residues of these compounds in waters must be controlled and monitored. According to drinking water guidelines, the maximum acceptable concentrations established by the European Union (98/83/EC) [1] are 0.1 and 0.5 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for individual or total pesticides respectively. In this sense, the determination of pesticides at these low concentration values requires the development of sensitive and selective techniques, mainly based on GC or LC combined with selective detectors such as NPD [2] or sophisticated detection techniques such as mass spectrometry [3].

In any case, the monitoring and detection of OPP residues in water sources with complex matrices requires the development of pre-treatment and sampling steps in order to enhance sensitivity. In this sense, different sample preparation techniques such as the classical LLE [4] and DLLME [5], as well as other novel techniques such as SBSE [6] have been used for the extraction of OPPs from water samples, whereas SPE with C18-based material [7,8] and SPME [9] are the most common techniques used for enrichment of these analytes. However, these SPE methods have some disadvantages, such as limited selectivity and poor reusability, whereas for SPME the fibers are fragile and relatively expensive [3,10]. In this sense, there is a considerable interest in developing new selective and efficient materials for extracting and isolating components from complex environmental matrices [11].

Mesoporous silica materials have received a lot of attention due to their favorable properties (e.g. mechanical, thermal and chemical stability), low density, good biocompatibility, easy and diverse controlling of particle size and morphologies [12]. Due to these unique features, they can be used as size-selective scaffolds to allow the adsorption of small molecules as well as large molecules by size-exclusion mechanism. In addition, they show high surface areas (up to 1000 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$) and pore volumes, jointly with a wide range of post-modification functionalities, which makes these materials attractive SPE sorbents [13].

The preparation of mesoporous silica materials can be achieved through the atrane route, where the introduction of surfactants as “templates” permits a fine control of the mesopore range compared to the classical sol-gel process thus expanding the range of applications of silica-based materials [14]. In this route, TEOS is commonly used as a

1 silicon source, whereas the usually used surfactant is the CTAB. Within mesoporous
2 silicas, MCM-41 is the most studied and applied material; however, other silicas such
3 as UVM-7, which can be considered as a nanometric version of MCM-41, have been
4 described. The most outstanding feature concerning of these materials is their peculiar
5 architecture: a continuous network constructed from aggregated small mesoporus
6 nanoparticles that generate a non-ordered system of large pores (between large-meso
7 and macro). It results in a material with high surface area and a highly accessible pore
8 system [15]. In addition, these mesoporous materials can be easily modified by
9 incorporation of different elements to these silica structures, in order to improve their
10 selective properties. In fact, several materials with M-UVM-7 structure containing a
11 diversity of dopant agents have been prepared [16,17]. In this sense, the addition of
12 titanium and iron to the silica network could be addressed in order to enhance the
13 adsorption properties of these materials towards for P-containing compounds, such as
14 OPPs [18,19]. In this sense, amino-modified UVM-7 materials have been only used as
15 sorbents in few studies, focused on environmental analysis, for the determination of
16 metallic ions [20].

27 On the other hand, sorbents based on conventional sol-gel process have been used in
28 the extraction of wide range of analytes by SPME [21,22]. However, a few studies
29 focused on applications of hybrid sol-gel materials as SPE sorbents have been
30 reported [10,23]. In this sense, we have recently developed cyclodextrin-silica
31 microporous composites (as host-guest complexes) as sorbent phases applied either in
32 air samplers [24] or SPE cartridges [25] to the effective retention of several pollutants
33 from environmental samples.

39 The aim of this work is to study the potential use of mesoporus silica materials based
40 on UVM-7 structure doped with Ti and Fe as SPE sorbents for extraction of OPPs in
41 water samples followed their analysis by GC-NPD. In addition, a comparison with silica
42 materials modified with immobilized CDs was initially done. The material that provided
43 the best extraction performance was selected and its relevant features (such as
44 breakthrough volume, reusability, etc.) were established. The optimal SPE procedure
45 was then applied to the preconcentration of OPPs in environmental water samples.
46 Additionally, these results were compared with those obtained with a commercial C18
47 SPE sorbent.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents

OPP standards such as ethoprophos, diazinon, methyl chlorpyrifos (chlorpyrifos-m), methyl tolclofos (tolclofos-m), fenitrothion, malathion, chlorpyrifos and parathion were from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Ultrapure water from an Adrona (Riga, Latvia) purification system was employed. All solvents used in extraction and analysis procedures were from HPLC grade quality: ethanol, n-hexane, dichloromethane, ethyl acetate from Scharlau (Barcelona, Spain) and MeOH, ACN, tetrahydrofuran and acetone from VWR Chemicals (Radnor, PA, USA).

For synthesis of silica-based materials, the following reagents were used: TEOS, triethanolamine, CTAB, tetrabutyl orthotitanate, iron chloride (II) tetra hydrate and ethanol were used from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland), 3-isocyanatepropyltriethoxysilane from Sigma-Aldrich, β - and γ -CD from CycloLab (Budapest, Hungary).

A standard stock multicomponent solution of OPPs was prepared. Working standard solutions were prepared by dilution of this stock mixture with ultrapure water. All pesticide solutions were stored in darkness at 4°C.

Additionally, for sample analysis commercial C18 cartridges (Varian Bond Elut, 200 mg) were used as reference sorbents for sample enrichment of OPPs.

Instrumentation

HRTEM images of silica-based materials were obtained using Jeol (Tokyo, Japan) model JEM-2100F microscope operated at 200 kV. Images were obtained using a MegaView III camera provided with the AnalySIS image data acquisition system. Moreover, EDX data was collected by using an XL30 ESEM scanning electron microscope.

Surface area, pore size and volume were measured by porosimetry using nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms. The isotherms were recorded at 77 K with a Micrometrics ASAP2010 automated sorption analyzer. The specific surface areas were calculated from the adsorption data in low-pressure range using BET model. Likewise, X-ray diffractograms were obtained using Cu K α radiation (Seifert 3000TT θ - θ).

A Vac Elut 20 connected to a vacuum pump system (CKNF model N 0.26.3 AN 18) was employed to treat the samples through SPE. Samples were previously filtered with nylon 0.45 μ m Sartorius Stedim Biotech filters.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

OPPs were determined using an Agilent 7890A GC system from Agilent Technologies Inc. (Waldbronn, Germany) equipped with an ALS-7693A autosampler with a NPD system. The analytical column was an Agilent HP-5 (30 m x 0.32 mm x 0.25 μm film thickness). Separation was carried out using nitrogen as carrier gas at 1 mL min^{-1} flow rate, sample injection (0.5 μL) was done in splitless mode using the following temperature gradient: 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 min, followed by a ramp at 5 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ up to 170 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (hold 3 min), and ramp at 2 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ to 195 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (hold 1.5 min). Under these conditions, a good resolution was achieved for all pesticides with the exception of chlorpyrifos and parathion pair. Also, some analytical figures of merit were evaluated using an Agilent 5977A GC chromatogram coupled to a single quadrupole MS detector. For this purpose, the same separation conditions indicated above were used and selective on monitoring mode was used for pesticide analysis. The specific ions monitored for each pesticide are given in Table S1.

On the other hand, to evaluate the non-retained OPPs in the sorbents, a LaChrom chromatograph was used, which was equipped with a LaChrom L-7100 pump, a Hitachi oven, a VWR L-7614 degasser, an Agilent Interface 35900E processor and a LaChrom L-7614 UV-Vis detector at 225 nm. The separation was carried out using a C18 ZORBAX Eclipse Plus column (4.6 x 100 mm, 3.5 μm particle size) at 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and at a constant flow of 1 mL min^{-1} , with MeOH:water as mobile phase under elution gradient conditions as follows: from 0-7 min from 50:50 (v/v) MeOH- H_2O increasing progressively up pure MeOH (to 60:40 (v/v) for 7-12 min; 80:20 (v/v) for 12-15 min, and 100% MeOH for 2 more min). The injection volume was 20 μL . In this case, all analytes were separated properly under described conditions.

Preparation of mesoporous silica materials

The synthesis of UVM-7 materials was based in a previous work [14] and they were prepared by a one-pot surfactant-assisted procedure, which is a modification of the so-called atrane route [17,26]. All of them were prepared by the same general method, and using the following molar ratios of reagents: 2-x Si:x M:7 TEA:0.5 CTAB:180 H_2O . In a typical synthesis of UVM-7 pure silica, 11.2 mL of TEOS and 25 mL of TEAH were mixed at 140 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and then 4.56 g of CTAB were added to the mixture at 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Afterwards, 180 mL of water were slowly added with vigorous stirring at 85 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. This mixture was aged at room temperature overnight. The resulting powder was collected by filtration, washed with water and ethanol, and air-dried. To prepare the final mesoporous material, the as-synthesized solid was calcined at 550 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 h. Heteroelement (M) incorporation in UVM-7 was achieved by simply adding variable

1 amounts of the respective metallic precursor to the silatrane containing solution, and
2 following the procedure described above. In this case, 0.65 mL of TBOT and 0.38 g of
3 $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were added in the first reaction step in order to obtain the Ti- or Fe-UVM-7
4 materials (with a Si/M = 25 molar ratio).
5
6

7 *Preparation of silica materials modified with immobilized CDs*

8
9

10 Sol-gel materials modified CDs were synthesized based on a prior study of our
11 research group [25]. The stoichiometry of these materials corresponds to the general
12 formula: $(\text{CD})_x\text{SiO}_{1.5}(\text{OH})_{0.5} \cdot 0.7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where the x value depends, among other
13 parameters, on the CD type. First, a functionalization of CD with silane group through
14 the reaction with 3-isocyanatopropyltriethoxysilane was done [27]. Then, the
15 condensation of this CD with TEOS resulted in a xerogel with immobilized CDs. After
16 that, the material was dried properly and it was sieved at particle size below 600 μm .
17 Using this procedure, two different materials were synthesized containing β - and γ -CD
18 (stoichiometric x-values of 0.0007 and 0.016 for β - and γ -CD, respectively). The
19 characterization of these materials was described in previous works [25,28].
20
21
22
23
24
25
26

27 *SPE protocol and analysis of real water samples*

28
29

30 For the preparation of the SPE cartridges, 50 mg of the UVM-7 materials (either pure or
31 doped with Ti or Fe) were packed between two polyethylene frits (20 μm) into 3 mL
32 empty propylene cartridges. For silica-based materials modified with β - or γ -CDs, 100
33 mg of each solid phase were placed into empty propylene cartridges.
34
35
36

37 The optimum SPE conditions were achieved with 75 mg of Ti25-UVM-7 material, which
38 was previously conditioned with 5 mL of MeOH and 5 mL of ultrapure water. Next, a
39 known volume of ultrapure water or sample water spiked with OPPs was passed
40 through the cartridges. Then, the cartridge was dried with air for 5 min and analytes
41 were eluted with 1 mL of hexane and 1 mL of ethyl acetate followed by GC-NPD
42 analysis. In all SPE stages, the flow rate was 0.9 mL min^{-1} .
43
44
45
46
47

48 Water samples from different sources such as well (Borriana, Castelló, Spain) and
49 irrigation (Algemesí, València) waters were collected. Also, waste water samples were
50 taken from the effluent and influent of a wastewater treatment plant. The pre-cleaned
51 bottles were covered with aluminium foil and stored in the dark at 4 °C until analysis.
52 Prior to analysis, samples were filtered to remove any particulate matter.
53
54
55
56

57 These real water samples were analyzed according to the protocol described above.
58 To evaluate the influence of matrix on pesticide recovery, these samples were spiked
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 with the OPPs at several levels of concentrations ($12.5-50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) in triplicate.
2 Additionally, these samples were analyzed using a commercial C18 cartridge since it is
3 often used as a reference sorbent in environmental analysis for sample enrichment of
4 OPPs [29,30]. In this case, the elution was carried out by using 2 mL of ethyl acetate
5 and 2 mL of dichloromethane followed by injection into GC system.
6
7
8
9

10 **Results and discussion**

11
12 In this work, we explore the ability of two silica-based porous materials as SPE
13 supports for the pesticide preconcentration in complex water samples. The two solids
14 differ both in the organization of the pore system as well as the interaction with the
15 analytes. In the case of xerogels containing CDs a unimodal micropore system is
16 present, whereas the UVM-7, as previously mentioned, can be considered as a
17 bimodal pore system combining meso and large pores. Regards to the sorbent-analyte
18 interaction, in the case of the Ti/Fe-UVM-7 solids, the local affinity of the phosphorus
19 moiety of the pesticides for Ti or Fe sites must be the responsible factor which would
20 provide an enhanced interaction. On the other hand, in the case of the CD-based
21 derivatives, the interaction must be controlled by the host-guest inclusion typical of
22 these supports.
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31

32 *Characterization of mesoporous and immobilized CD silica-based materials*

33
34 The synthesized mesoporous silica materials were firstly characterized by EDX, and
35 molar ratios Si/M of 19 and 22 were obtained for Ti and Fe UVM-7 solids, respectively.
36 TEM micrographs were also obtained for these materials (Fig. 1). As it can be seen,
37 the incorporation of Ti and Fe did not modify the typical architecture of the UVM-7 pure
38 silicas. A representative TEM image of the Ti-UVM-7 derivative is given in Fig.1A
39 showing the organization based on the aggregation of primary mesoporous
40 nanoparticles (inset of Fig. 1A), where an additional hierarchic continuous pore system
41 of non-ordered large pores is evidenced. The Ti incorporation did not induce the
42 formation of ordered nanodomains along the silica network (see Fig. 1B), which
43 suggests a good heteroelement dispersion. This finding was consistent with STEM
44 mapping results, which showed a homogeneous distribution of Ti along the silica
45 network (see inset in Fig. 1B). However, in the case of UVM-7 material doped with Fe
46 (see Fig. 1C), the presence of well-dispersed small ordered nanodomains of iron oxide
47 were evidenced. The different incorporation mode for both elements must be attributed
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 to the less-favored exchange between Si (IV) and Fe (III) species compared to Ti (IV)
2 in which case can be considered as an isomorphous substitution.

3 The XRD patterns of these UVM-7 materials were also taken (Fig. S1). In all cases, a
4 broad band at low angles (2° (2θ)) was observed, which is typical of materials with a
5 continuous network of mesopores with an hexagonal pseudo-order [16].
6

7 Then, the surface area and pore-size distribution of the prepared UVM-7 materials
8 were determined from the nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms (Fig. S2). In UVM-
9 7 silica-based materials, two adsorption steps were evidenced, thus confirming their
10 bimodal framework and its high accessibility [16]. As shown in Table 1, surface areas
11 of the pure and doped UVM-7 materials were similar as well as the existence of
12 mesopores (2.8 nm) and large macropores (33-39 nm), thus confirming the bimodal
13 pore system in the silica framework.
14

15 For comparison, CD-silica composite materials were also included. These materials
16 were previously characterized (HRTEM micrographs and morphological features)
17 [25,28]. As shown in Table 1 and in Fig. S3, these xerogel materials showed the
18 presence of micropores (pore size < 0.7 nm) and provided lower surface areas over
19 mesoporous materials, mainly for γ -CD composite material since addition of this CD
20 caused a significant decrease of the surface area.
21

22 *SPE optimization*

23 The study of sorbent nature was firstly evaluated by testing either pure UVM-7 silica as
24 well as doped with Ti or Fe. For this purpose, SPE cartridges containing 50 mg of each
25 material (UVM-7, Ti25-UVM-7 and Fe25-UVM-7) was selected. Thus, 25 mL of
26 ultrapure water containing target OPPs in concentrations of 125 - 500 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ were
27 loaded into each cartridge. After elution with 4 mL of ethyl acetate, the results of this
28 study showed that Ti25-UVM-7 gave the best recovery efficiencies for OPPs (reaching
29 values up to 69.1%), and it was selected for the following studies.
30

31 Then, this material was compared with sol-gel materials with immobilized CDs. Thus,
32 cartridges containing 50 mg of Ti25-UVM-7 or 100 mg (minimum amount of material to
33 be properly packed) of CD-based materials were prepared and 25 mL of deionized
34 water spiked with OPPs was introduced in each cartridge. Then, analytes were eluted
35 with ethyl acetate. The results showed that these latter materials using either β - or γ -
36 CDs provided large retention values (93.8-100 %) for OPPs containing aromatic rings,
37 mainly those that have chlorinated functional groups (chlorpyrifos-m, tolclofos-m and
38 chlorpyrifos). It could be explained by the ability of CDs for form host-guest complexes
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 with OPPs containing these functional groups. Indeed, low retentions, and therefore
2 low recoveries (below 20 %), were obtained for analytes without aromatic groups (e.g.
3 ethoprophos and malathion) using β -CD-based sol-gel material. A slight improvement
4 in the recovery values (up to 25 %) was obtained for these analytes when γ -CD
5 material was tried, probably due to the bigger size of this CD.
6
7

8 In contrast, using Ti25-UVM-7 material, retentions over 80 % were obtained for all
9 analytes, and in some cases close to 100 %. Although these values were obtained
10 using an un-optimized elution procedure, these results clearly demonstrated that UVM-
11 7-based materials are more appropriate than sol-gel materials modified with CDs. The
12 enhanced ability of Ti-UVM-7 solid to interact with a large variety of P-containing
13 pesticides when compared to the CD-containing silica xerogels is based on two
14 aspects: the higher accessibility derived of the open architecture of UVM-7 solids, and
15 a support-analyte interaction more generic and independent of the pesticide size.
16
17

18 Then, several SPE parameters such as amount of sorbent, types and volumes of
19 eluting solvents, pH and ionic strength of sample were studied. This optimization
20 procedure was performed with deionized water spiked with OPPs as a test mixture. In
21 particular, OPP concentrations used during SPE optimization were: 50 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for
22 diazinon; 125 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for ethoprophos, tolclofos-m, fenitrothion and parathion; and 250
23 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for chlorpyrifos, malathion and chlorpyrifos-m.
24
25

26 The amount of sorbent (25-100 mg) was firstly studied using Ti25-UMV-7 as filler of the
27 SPE cartridge. As can be seen in Fig. 2, the best recoveries were found at 75 mg,
28 being this amount chosen for further studies.
29
30

31 In order to increase the recoveries, the influence of eluent type was then considered. In
32 this sense, several eluting solvents of different polarities namely ethyl acetate, ACN,
33 MeOH, dichloromethane, hexane and tetrahydrofuran were investigated [3,11,31,32].
34 For this purpose, an elution volume of 4 mL was selected. As shown in Fig. 3 best
35 results were achieved using ethyl acetate and hexane, depending on the analyte. Thus,
36 both solvents were selected to carry out the study of eluent solvent volume. In this way,
37 volumes from 1 to 4 mL of hexane or ethyl acetate were investigated to assure the
38 minimum but enough volume required to elute the retained OPPs to achieve the
39 highest sensitivity. The highest recoveries (83.4-108.3 %) were obtained when 1 mL of
40 hexane followed by 1 mL of ethyl acetate were used.
41
42

43 Then, the influence of pH on the recoveries by changing the pH value of the sample
44 solution between 4.0 and 7.0 was studied. For this study, the loading step was
45 adequately adjusted to the pH conditions to achieve the highest extraction efficiency.
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 Results indicated that sample pH did not affect the analytes retention, as their
2 properties acid-base are practically negligible, and working pH range are above silica
3 isoelectric point (2-3) [33]. Thus, neutral pH was chosen for next studies.
4

5 The effect of ionic strength was also studied in order to reduce the solubility of analytes
6 in the aqueous phase while enhancing their partitioning into the sorbent [34]. Different
7 contents of sodium chloride (up to 2 M) in the sample were studied. Results indicated
8 that when salt concentration increased, the recoveries for all the OPPs decreased,
9 probably due to the competitive interaction of Na⁺ ions with silanol moieties.
10 Consequently, the use of NaCl was discarded.
11

12 In order to obtain reliable analytical results and high preconcentration factors, it is
13 relevant to achieve satisfactory recoveries for all analytes in as large sample volume as
14 possible. In order to establish the breakthrough volume, variable volumes (between 25
15 and 100 mL) of the OPPs solution were passed through the SPE material.
16

17 Experimental results showed recoveries comprised between 86.9-113.3 % for OPPs up
18 to 50 mL, whereas a considerable decrease in the recoveries of OPPs was observed at
19 volumes of 100 mL. Consequently, 50 mL was adopted as the volume for the analysis
20 of real water samples.
21

22 The loading capacity of SPE sorbent was also evaluated by loading different amounts
23 of OPPs (50 mL of spiked 4-250 µg L⁻¹ deionized water). Results indicated that no
24 significant differences in the recoveries were found for the different concentrations
25 tested, which suggested that studied material could be properly used for SPE
26 extraction within these concentrations.
27

28 *Analytical figures of merit*

29 The optimized SPE protocol was validated with respect to linearity, sensitivity and
30 precision. Calibration curves were prepared and injected twice. The limit of detection
31 (LOD), as well as the limit of quantification (LOQ), were estimated according to the
32 latest IUPAC recommendations, with a confidence level of 95 % [35]. Linearity range
33 was estimated following these recommendations, considering the LOQ as the lower
34 limit of linearity [35]. In the same way, calibration solutions were injected into a GC-MS
35 system to evaluate these parameters for chlorpyrifos and parathion separately, as well
36 as to establish the linear range and sensitivity of the method (Table 2). As it can be
37 seen, LODs were lower than 1.3 µg L⁻¹ for several OPPs, such as ethoprophos,
38 diazinon, chlorpyrifos-m and tolclofos-m using NPD detector, whereas using GC-MS
39 instrumentations LODs below 1.4 µg L⁻¹ were achieved for all analytes.
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 The precision of the SPE combined with GC-NPD method was evaluated by studying
2 the intra- and inter-day repeatabilities of extractions of 50 mL of spiked water samples.
3 The intra-day precision was determined by analyzing three replicates within a given
4 day, whereas the inter-day precision was estimated by analyzing three series of three
5 independent experiments carried out on three different days (see Table 2). The method
6 showed a good precision with relative standard deviation (RSD) values below 12 %.
7

8 Also, good extraction efficiencies were achieved (between 81-104 %), and enrichment
9 factors for all the analytes were calculated by considering 50 mL of sample volume and
10 2 mL of final extract. They were in the range from 20.4 to 26.1.
11

12 *Sample analysis and matrix influence*

13 The proposed SPE protocol using Ti25-UVM-7 material was applied for the analysis of
14 different environmental water samples and the study of the matrix influence. Table 3
15 shows the recovery values obtained in several matrices. As it can be seen in Table 2
16 and 3, for Ti25-UVM-7 material, recovery rates in these water samples were
17 significantly affected by the matrix. In any case, the results showed that WWTP water
18 underwent the highest matrix effect, whereas the well water showed the lowest one,
19 although the influence was, in general, similar for all matrices. Anyway, the results
20 obtained demonstrate that the use of standard addition calibration would be advisable,
21 for future applications, due to the matrix type influence.
22

23 To validate the feasibility of the proposed SPE protocol using Ti25-UVM-7 material, a
24 commercial C18 SPE sorbent (see *Chemicals and reagents*) was also used for
25 comparison. Thus, both SPE protocols were applied to the determination of these
26 OPPs in seven water samples collected from the following origins: WWTP influent (M1)
27 and effluent (M2) channels, Borriana irrigation ditch (M3), several Borriana water wells
28 (M4, M5, M6) and Algesesí irrigation network (M7). As shown in Table 4, most of OPP
29 concentrations were below LODs and all of them below LOQs using both Ti25-UVM-7
30 and C18 materials. Tolclofos-m and diazinon were present in samples M1, M2 and M5,
31 whereas in the rest of samples these target OPPs or others were not found.
32

33 Additionally, it seems relevant that OPP concentrations found in M1 and M2 samples
34 (influent and effluent WWTP water) were quite similar, since these plants are not
35 designed to remove micropollutants [36].
36

37 Since no target OPPs were detected, some water samples (M1 and M3) were spiked
38 (M1S and M3S) and analyzed by both SPE protocols. The results obtained (Table 5)
39 showed that both methodologies are completely comparable (comparison of variances
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1 by Fisher-Snedecor's test and comparison of means by Student's test, 95% of
2 confidence level).

3
4 Then, the reusability of Ti25-UVM-7 material in real matrix (irrigation water) was also
5 evaluated. The results indicated the cartridges were reused until three times without a
6 significant decrease in the recoveries for OPPs (differences on the recoveries below 5
7 % for all OPPs). In addition, this re-used solid phase can be re-calcined (5 h) and used
8 again for new extraction cartridges reaching large recovery values and differences
9 under 8 % from first use.

10
11 At sight of previous results, our material showed similar results for analysis of real
12 samples compared to commercial C18 cartridges, although a great advantage over this
13 sorbent was its reusability, which undoubtedly makes more economically attractive its
14 application to extract these OPPs in complex sample matrices.

15
16 The developed material was also compared with previous extraction methods reported
17 by Korrani *et al.* [10] that use sol-gel silica mesoporous materials as SPE sorbent. In
18 particular, the mean recovery values assayed for diazinon in this work were in the
19 same order of magnitude than those previously found in water samples. However, this
20 analytical parameter or others (e.g. reusability) were evaluated using spiked deionized
21 water or samples with relatively simple matrices (tap water, drinking water and mineral
22 water) in contrast to those considered here. Concerning to the LODs, our values were
23 better than those reported using SPE with cyano cartridges [10], although slightly
24 higher than that found by Korrani *et al.* (0.4 vs 0.1 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for diazinon). In any case, the
25 SPE protocol developed here constitutes a good alternative for the effective extraction
26 of OPPs since it can be performed in a short time (ca. 6 samples per hour) and with
27 low cost.

28 29 30 31 32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40 41 42 43 44 **Conclusions**

45
46 In this work, a novel SPE sorbent based on a UVM-7 mesoporous silica doped with Ti
47 has been synthesized, and applied to the extraction of several OPPs in water samples
48 followed GC-NPD analysis. Several mesoporous silica (pure, Ti- and Fe- doped UVM-
49 7) as well as immobilized CD silica-based materials were firstly prepared and tested as
50 SPE sorbents for OPP extraction. As result of this study, Ti25-UVM-7 material was
51 selected as the best solid phase. After optimization of extraction protocol, high recovery
52 values (> 81 %) were achieved with spiked deionized water. Then, the SPE protocol
53 was applied to the extraction of OPPs in complex water samples and matrix effect was
54 demonstrated in these matrices, being recommended a standard addition calibration.

1 The method was also validated using C18 commercial cartridges, and both protocols
2 gave comparable results for the analysis of spiked real samples. The synthesized
3 material showed satisfactory retentions for these analytes and better reusability than
4 the commercial support. The protocol developed here also provided satisfactory LODs
5 using common equipment accessible in most analytical laboratories, as well as LODs
6 in the range 0.2-1.4 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ using a GC-MS system. In summary, the present SPE
7 method is simple, cost-effective, and showed a good reusability of material.
8
9

10 **Acknowledgments**

11 This work was supported by the MINECO of Spain and FEDER (MAT2015-64139-C4-
12 2-R) and the Generalitat Valenciana (PROMETEO/2016/145). E. P-C thanks the MEC
13 for an FPU grant for PhD studies. C. B-S thanks Universitat de València for a grant for
14 PhD studies.
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

References

- [1] Consejo de la Unión Europea, Directiva 98/83/CE del Consejo, 1998. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/ES/TXT/?uri=celex:31998L0083>.
- [2] M.V. Russo, P. Avino, G. Cinelli, I. Notardonato, Sampling of organophosphorus pesticides at trace levels in the atmosphere using XAD-2 adsorbent and analysis by gas chromatography coupled with nitrogen-phosphorus and ion-trap mass spectrometry detectors, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 404 (2012) 1517–1527. doi:10.1007/s00216-012-6205-2.
- [3] S. Meseguer-Lloret, S. Torres-Cartas, M. Catalá-Icardo, E.F. Simó-Alfonso, J.M. Herrero-Martínez, Extraction and preconcentration of organophosphorus pesticides in water by using a polymethacrylate-based sorbent modified with magnetic nanoparticles, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 409 (2017) 3561–3571. doi:10.1007/s00216-017-0294-x.
- [4] D. Barceló, Environmental Protection Agency and other methods for the determination of priority pesticides and their transformation products in water, *J. Chromatogr. A.* 643 (1993) 117–143. doi:10.1016/0021-9673(93)80546-K.
- [5] S. Samadi, H. Sereshti, Y. Assadi, Ultra-preconcentration and determination of thirteen organophosphorus pesticides in water samples using solid-phase extraction followed by dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction and gas chromatography with flame photometric detection, *J. Chromatogr. A.* 1219 (2012) 61–65. doi:10.1016/j.chroma.2011.11.019.
- [6] M. Tankiewicz, J. Fenik, M. Biziuk, Solventless and solvent-minimized sample preparation techniques for determining currently used pesticides in water samples: A review, *Talanta.* 86 (2011) 8–22. doi:10.1016/j.talanta.2011.08.056.
- [7] M.R. Hadjmohammadi, M. Peyrovi, P. Biparva, Comparison of C18 silica and multi-walled carbon nanotubes as the adsorbents for the solid-phase extraction of Chlorpyrifos and Phosalone in water samples using HPLC, *J. Sep. Sci.* 33 (2010) 1044–1051. doi:10.1002/jssc.200900494.
- [8] M.E. Báez, M. Rodríguez, O. Lastra, P. Contreras, Solid Phase Extraction of Organophosphorus, Triazine, and Triazole-Derived Pesticides from Water Samples. A Critical Study, *HRC J. High Resolut. Chromatogr.* 20 (1997) 591–596. doi:10.1002/jhrc.1240201105.
- [9] L. Pelit, T.N. Dizdaş, Preparation and application of a polythiophene solid-phase microextraction fiber for the determination of endocrine-disruptor pesticides in

well waters, *J. Sep. Sci.* 36 (2013) 3234–3241. doi:10.1002/jssc.201300633.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- [10] Z. Soutoudehnia Korrani, W.A. Wan Ibrahim, H. Rashidi Nodeh, H.Y. Aboul-Enein, M.M. Sanagi, Simultaneous preconcentration of polar and non-polar organophosphorus pesticides from water samples by using a new sorbent based on mesoporous silica, *J. Sep. Sci.* 39 (2016) 1144–1151. doi:10.1002/jssc.201500896.
- [11] C.R.M. Vigna, L.S.R. Morais, C.H. Collins, I.C.S.F. Jardim, Poly(methyloctylsiloxane) immobilized on silica as a sorbent for solid-phase extraction of some pesticides, *J. Chromatogr. A.* 1114 (2006) 211–215. doi:10.1016/j.chroma.2006.03.034.
- [12] A. Weller, E.J. Carrasco-Correa, C. Belenguer-Sapiña, A. Mauri-Aucejo, P. Amorós, J.M. Herrero-Martínez, Organo-silica hybrid capillary monolithic column with mesoporous silica particles for separation of small aromatic molecules, *Microchim. Acta.* 184 (2017) 3799–3808. doi:10.1007/s00604-017-2404-z.
- [13] N. Casado, D. Pérez-Quintanilla, S. Morante-Zarcelero, I. Sierra, Current development and applications of ordered mesoporous silicas and other sol–gel silica-based materials in food sample preparation for xenobiotics analysis, *TrAC - Trends Anal. Chem.* 88 (2017) 167–184. doi:10.1016/j.trac.2017.01.001.
- [14] J. El Haskouri, J.M. Morales, D. Ortiz de Zárate, L. Ferna, J. Latorre, C. Guillem, A. Beltrán, D. Beltrán, P. Amorós, Nanoparticulated Silicas with Bimodal Porosity : Chemical Control of the Pore Sizes Nanoparticulated Silicas with Bimodal Porosity : Chemical Control of the Pore Sizes, 47 (2008) 8267–8277. doi:10.1021/ic800893a.
- [15] M. Pérez-Cabero, F.A. Esteve-Turrillas, D. Beltrán, P. Amorós, Hierarchical porous carbon with designed pore architecture and study of its adsorptive properties, *Solid State Sci.* 12 (2010) 15–25. doi:10.1016/j.solidstatesciences.2009.09.017.
- [16] J. El Haskouri, D. Ortiz de Zárate, C. Guillem, J. Latorre, M. Caldés, A. Beltrán, D. Beltrán, A.B. Descalzo, G. Rodríguez-López, R. Martínez-Máñez, M.D. Marcos, P. Amorós, Silica-based powders and monoliths with bimodal pore systems., *Chem. Commun. (Camb).* (2002) 330–331. doi:10.1039/b110883b.
- [17] J. El Haskouri, D. Ortiz de Zárate, F. Perez-Pla, A. Cervilla, C. Guillem, J. Latorre, M.D. Marcos, A. Beltrán, D. Beltrán, P. Amorós, Improving epoxide production using Ti-UVM-7 porous nanosized catalysts, *New J. Chem.* 26 (2002)

1093–1095. doi:10.1039/b205856c.

- 1
2 [18] R. Mahmoud, S.A. Moaty, F. Mohamed, A. Farghali, Comparative Study of
3 Single and Multiple Pollutants System Using Ti-Fe Chitosan LDH Adsorbent with
4 High Performance in Wastewater Treatment, *J. Chem. Eng. Data.* 62 (2017)
5 3703–3722. doi:10.1021/acs.jced.7b00453.
6
7
8
9 [19] J. Lu, D. Liu, J. Hao, G. Zhang, B. Lu, Phosphate removal from aqueous
10 solutions by a nano-structured Fe-Ti bimetal oxide sorbent, *Chem. Eng. Res.*
11 *Des.* 93 (2015) 652–661. doi:10.1016/j.cherd.2014.05.001.
12
13 [20] H. Shirkhanloo, M. Ghazaghi, A. Rashidi, A. Vahid, Arsenic speciation based on
14 amine-functionalized bimodal mesoporous silica nanoparticles by ultrasound
15 assisted-dispersive solid-liquid multiple phase microextraction, *Microchem. J.*
16 130 (2017) 137–146. doi:10.1016/j.microc.2016.08.013.
17
18 [21] A. Es-haghi, V. Hosseinasab, H. Bagheri, Preparation, characterization, and
19 applications of a novel solid-phase microextraction fiber by sol-gel technology on
20 the surface of stainless steel wire for determination of poly cyclic aromatic
21 hydrocarbons in aquatic environmental samples, *Anal. Chim. Acta.* 813 (2014)
22 48–55. doi:10.1016/j.aca.2014.01.005.
23
24 [22] W.A. Wan Ibrahim, H. Farhani, M.M. Sanagi, H.Y. Aboul-Enein, Solid phase
25 microextraction using new sol-gel hybrid polydimethylsiloxane-2-hydroxymethyl-
26 18-crown-6-coated fiber for determination of organophosphorous pesticides, *J.*
27 *Chromatogr. A.* 1217 (2010) 4890–4897. doi:10.1016/j.chroma.2010.05.050.
28
29 [23] W.A. Wan Ibrahim, K.V. Veloo, M.M. Sanagi, Novel sol-gel hybrid
30 methyltrimethoxysilane-tetraethoxysilane as solid phase extraction sorbent for
31 organophosphorus pesticides, *J. Chromatogr. A.* 1229 (2012) 55–62.
32 doi:10.1016/j.chroma.2012.01.022.
33
34 [24] A.R. Mauri-Aucejo, P. Ponce-Català, C. Belenguer-Sapiña, P. Amorós,
35 Determination of phenolic compounds in air by using cyclodextrin-silica hybrid
36 microporous composite samplers, *Talanta.* 134 (2015) 560–567.
37 doi:10.1016/j.talanta.2014.11.057.
38
39 [25] A. Mauri-Aucejo, P. Amorós, A. Moragues, C. Guillem, C. Belenguer-Sapiña,
40 Comparison of the solid-phase extraction efficiency of a bounded and an
41 included cyclodextrin-silica microporous composite for polycyclic aromatic
42 hydrocarbons determination in water samples, *Talanta.* 156–157 (2016) 95–103.
43 doi:10.1016/j.talanta.2016.05.011.
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
- [26] S. Cabrera, J. El Haskouri, C. Guillem, J. Latorre, A. Beltrán-Porter, D. Beltrán-Porter, M.D. Marcos, P. Amorós, Generalised syntheses of ordered mesoporous oxides: The atrane route, *Solid State Sci.* 2 (2000) 405–420. doi:10.1016/S1293-2558(00)00152-7.
- [27] S.T. Mahmud, L.D. Wilson, Synthesis and characterization of surface-modified mesoporous silica materials with β -cyclodextrin, *Cogent Chem.* 2 (2016) 1–19. doi:10.1080/23312009.2015.1132984.
- [28] S. Soler-Seguí, C. Belenguer-Sapiña, P. Amorós, A. Mauri-Aucejo, Evaluation of a Cyclodextrin-silica Hybrid Microporous Composite for the Solid-phase Extraction of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons, *Anal. Sci.* 32 (2016) 659–665. doi:10.2116/analsci.32.659.
- [29] H. Dabrowska, Ł. Dabrowski, M. Biziuk, J. Gaca, J. Namieśnik, Solid-phase extraction clean-up of soil and sediment extracts for the determination of various types of pollutants in a single run, *J. Chromatogr. A.* 1003 (2003) 29–42. doi:10.1016/S0021-9673(03)00849-5.
- [30] A.R. Fernandez-Alba, A. Agüera, M. Contreras, G. Peñuela, I. Ferrer, D. Barceló, Comparison of various sample handling and analytical procedures for the monitoring of pesticides and metabolites in ground waters, *J. Chromatogr. A.* 823 (1998) 35–47. doi:10.1016/S0021-9673(98)00439-7.
- [31] S.L. McManus, C.E. Coxon, P.E. Mellander, M. Danaher, K.G. Richards, Hydrogeological characteristics influencing the occurrence of pesticides and pesticide metabolites in groundwater across the Republic of Ireland, *Sci. Total Environ.* 601–602 (2017) 594–602. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.05.082.
- [32] B. Maddah, S.S. Javadi, A. Mirzaei, M. Rahimi-Nasrabadi, Application of electrospun polystyrene nanofibers as solid phase extraction sorbent for the preconcentration of diazinon and fenitrothion in environmental waters, *J. Liq. Chromatogr. Relat. Technol.* 38 (2015) 208–214. doi:10.1080/10826076.2014.896820.
- [33] R.K. Iller, *The chemistry of silica*, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1979.
- [34] M. Yang, X. Xi, X. Wu, R. Lu, W. Zhou, S. Zhang, H. Gao, Vortex-assisted magnetic β -cyclodextrin/attapulgite-linked ionic liquid dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction coupled with high-performance liquid chromatography for the fast determination of four fungicides in water samples, *J. Chromatogr. A.* 1381 (2015) 37–47. doi:10.1016/j.chroma.2015.01.016.

1 [35] A.C. Olivieri, N.M. Faber, J. Ferré, R. Boqué, J.H. Kalivas, H. Mark, Uncertainty
2 estimation and figures of merit for multivariate calibration (IUPAC Technical
3 Report), *Pure Appl. Chem.* 78 (2006) 633–661. doi:10.1351/pac200678030633.
4

5 [36] N.I. Rousis, R. Bade, L. Bijlsma, E. Zuccato, J. V. Sancho, F. Hernandez, S.
6 Castiglioni, Monitoring a large number of pesticides and transformation products
7 in water samples from Spain and Italy, *Environ. Res.* 156 (2017) 31–38.
8 doi:10.1016/j.envres.2017.03.013.
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Table 1

Textural parameters of the studied materials.

Solid phase	BET surface area (m ² g ⁻¹)	Micropores/Mesopores		Macropores	
		Pore size (nm)	Pore volume (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	Pore size (nm)	Pore volume (cm ³ g ⁻¹)
UVM-7	922	2.76	0.76	38.56	0.82
Ti25-UVM7	967	2.76	0.78	33.28	0.77
Fe25-UVM-7	995	2.76	0.81	36.22	1.16
β-CD ^a	350	< 0.7	-	-	-
γ-CD ^a	< 10	< 0.7	-	-	-

^a Obtained from previous works [24,27].

Table 2

Analytical figures of merit of the proposed SPE protocol combined with GC-NPD method, and GC-MS systems.

Compound	Repeatability RSD (%)		Extraction efficiency (%)	EF	GC-NPD			GC-MS		
	Intra-day	Inter-day			Linearity ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	LOD ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	Linearity ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	LOD ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)
Ethoprophos	3.8	4.8	95 ± 2	23.7 ± 0.5	0.10-2.50 2.5	1.30 8	4.12 4	0.03-2.50 2.5	0.40 2	1.20 7
Diazinon	2.6	3.2	104.5 ± 1.5	26.1 ± 0.4	0.03-1.25 1.25	0.40 3	1.74 0	0.012-1.25 1.25	0.20 3	0.54 0
Chlorpyrifos-m	6.4	9.8	81 ± 4	20.4 ± 0.9	0.09-50.05 5	1.22 2	3.76 7	0.06-50.004 5	0.70 4	2.20 4
Tolclofos-m	3.2	6.0	84 ± 2	21.0 ± 0.6	0.09-2.50 2.5	1.20 8	3.82 3	0.02-2.50 2.5	0.20 6	0.70 2
Fenitrothion	7.8	12.0	90 ± 5	22.4 ± 1.2	0.2-2.50 14	3.15 7	9.347 3	0.04-2.50 2.5	0.50 7	1.72 4
Malathion	5.9	9.0	98 ± 4	24.5 ± 1.0	0.2-50.09 5	2.83 5	8.640 5	0.06-50.007 5	0.80 3	2.30 8
Chlorpyrifos	2.9	6.6	83 ± 2	10.3 ± 0.3	-	-	-	0.11-50.003 5	1.40 4	4.40 3
Parathion								0.03-50.015 5	0.40 6	1.24 9

Table 3

Matrix influence on the OPP recovery (%) using the proposed method.

Compound	C _{added} ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	WWTP water	Well water	Irrigation water
Ethoprophos	25.5	87 \pm 9	93 \pm 4	83 \pm 9
Diazinon	12.8	77 \pm 15	78 \pm 2	82 \pm 7
Chlorpyrifos-m	51.2	59 \pm 10	61 \pm 2	57 \pm 7
Tolclofos-m	25.7	59 \pm 11	57 \pm 2	55 \pm 11
Fenitrothion	25.3	48 \pm 5	69 \pm 4	52 \pm 7
Malathion	50.7	49 \pm 8	68.8 \pm 1.5	49 \pm 9

Table 5

Results obtained ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) for OPPs determination in spiked water samples (M1S and M3S), using Ti25-UVM-7 material and C18 commercial cartridges, and their relative error (%).

Compound	C_{added}	M1S				M3S			
		C18		Ti25-UVM-7		C18		Ti25-UVM-7	
		Conc.	Err.	Conc.	Err.	Conc.	Err.	Conc.	Err.
Ethoprophos	25.5	25.7 \pm 1.9	1.0	25.6 \pm 0.6	-0.4	25.4 \pm 0.6	-0.4	27.5 \pm 1.7	8.2
Diazinon	12.8	12.7 \pm 0.5	-1.2	13.8 \pm 0.6	1.8	13.1 \pm 0.3	1.8	13.9 \pm 0.4	8.1
Chlorpyrifos-m	51.2	50 \pm 4	-1.5	54 \pm 4	2.2	52 \pm 3	2.2	59 \pm 4	14.8
Tolclofos-m	25.7	25.2 \pm 1.7	-1.9	29 \pm 3	2.5	26.4 \pm 1.3	2.5	27.6 \pm 1.5	7.4
Fenitrothion	25.3	24.9 \pm 1.2	-1.7	23.3 \pm 0.8	2.3	26 \pm 3	2.3	29.5 \pm 1.4	16.5
Malathion	50.7	50 \pm 7	-0.8	51 \pm 3	1.4	51 \pm 2	1.4	50.9 \pm 1.4	0.4

Figure captions

Fig. 1. Representative HRTEM images of the mesoporous silica materials: (A) Ti25-UVM-7 in two different zooms, (B) Ti25-UVM-7 and its EDX mapping, and (C) Fe25-UVM-7. Part (C) shows small ordered microdomains of iron oxide.

Fig. 2. Effect of the amount of solid phase (Ti25-UVM-7) on the recovery of OPPs. Conditions: sample volume, 25 mL; eluent, 4 mL of ethyl acetate; deionized water spiked with 50 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of diazinon; 125 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of ethoprophos, tolclofos-m, fenitrothion and parathion; and 250 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of chlorpyrifos, malathion and chlorpyrifos-m.

Fig. 3. Effect of the type of eluting solvent on the recovery of OPPs. Conditions: sample volume, 25 mL; sorbent amount, 75 mg; eluent volume, 4 mL; the test mixture used was as indicated in Fig. 2.

Figure 1
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 2
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

Figure 3
[Click here to download high resolution image](#)

